

Distribution and genetic diversity of the invasive pest *Halyomorpha halys* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) in Belgium.

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Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	COI Analysis	2
2.1	Data from Belgium	2
2.2	Comparison to published sequences	10
3	COII Analysis	19
3.1	Data from Belgium	19
3.2	Comparison to published sequences	25
4	COI + COII Analysis	32
4.1	Data from Belgium	32
4.2	Comparison to published sequences	40

1 Introduction

We investigated the genetic diversity of the Brown Marmorated Stink Bug (BMSB) *Halyomorpha halys* in Belgium. This is the complete report of the analysis of genetic data. Please see the main text of the article for details.

In total, 99 specimens from 18 populations were captured and analysed. Two fragments (COI and COII) of the mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase gene were amplified from these specimens to analyze the genetic diversity of Belgian populations. We then compared the haplotypes found in Belgium to published sequences from the studies of Cesari et al. (2018, Insects) and Yan et al. (2021, BMC Genomic Data) + sequences retrieved on BOLD with COI + COII data.

2 COI Analysis

2.1 Data from Belgium

99 sequences were retrieved for COI fragment analysis with 9 distinct haplotypes. Haplotype diversity (i.e. the probability that two randomly chosen haplotypes are different; Nei & Tajima, 1981), $h = 0.77 \pm 0.02$. Nucleotide diversity (i.e. the average number of nucleotide differences per site between two DNA sequences from the population/sample of interest; Nei & Li, 1979), $\pi = 0.004 \pm 0.0024$

##

Haplotypes extracted from: d

##

Number of haplotypes: 9

Sequence length: 658

##

Haplotype labels and frequencies:

##

##	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
----	---	----	-----	----	---	----	-----	------	----

##	1	23	33	5	8	2	25	1	1
----	---	----	----	---	---	---	----	---	---

Iteration: 1 Number of links: 8Iteration: 2 Number of links: 8Iteration: 3 Number of link

Figure 1:

Simple haplotype network using the number of different nucleotides between haplotypes to compute the distance matrix. Network constructed using the randomized minimum spanning tree method (rmst; Paradis, 2018). Note that other methods (mst and msn) give the same result.

Figure 2:

Size the haplotypes according to their frequencies (square-rooted)

Figure 3:

Haplotype network by region (sqrt of haplotype freq)

- | | | |
|-------------|----------------|------------------------|
| ● Ezemaal | ● Lummen | ● Rik Gentbrugge |
| ● Heverlee | ● Melen | ● Rosoux |
| ● Jeuk | ● Mouscron | ● Saint-Trond |
| ● Kerkom | ● Neufchateau | ● Sint-Lambrechts-Herk |
| ● Kessel-Lo | ● Nieuwenhoven | ● Upigny |
| ● Lesdain | ● Rhisnes | ● Vlijtingen |

Figure 4:

Haplotype network by locality (sqrt of haplotype freq)

	H01	H03	H08	H23	H40c	H41	H41c	H42c	H49c
Ezemaal	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Heverlee	4	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Jeuk	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Kerkom	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kessel-Lo	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Lesdain	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lummen	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Melen	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mouscron	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Neufchateau	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Nieuwenhoven	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rhisnes	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rik Gentbrugge	9	7	24	0	1	0	6	1	0
Rosoux	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saint-Trond	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Sint-Lambrechts-Herk	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Upigny	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Vlijtingen	3	5	0	0	0	2	0	1	1

Haplotype distribution by locality

Locality	N	Hn	h	π
Vlijtingen	12	5	0.79	0.0039
Rik Gentbrugge	48	6	0.69	0.0039
Lesdain	2	1	0	0
Melen	2	2	1	0.0015
Rhisnes	3	2	0.67	0.002
Heverlee	6	3	0.6	0.0028
Lummen	1	1	/	/
Kessel-Lo	7	3	0.52	0.0033
Kerkom	1	1	/	/
Sint-Lambrechts-Herk	4	2	0.5	8e-04
Upigny	2	2	1	0.0015
Rosoux	3	1	0	0
Nieuwenhoven	2	1	0	0
Ezemaal	1	1	/	/
Saint-Trond	2	2	1	0.0106
Jeuk	1	1	/	/
Neufchateau	1	1	/	/
Mouscron	1	1	/	/

Summary table of MtDNA diversity by locality. N = sample size, Hn = number of haplotypes, h = haplotype diversity and π = nucleotide diversity.

Figure 5:

Alternatively, we can use the haploNet function which also computes haplotype network based on a parsimony network (TCS; Templeton et al., 1992). Haplotype network by locality (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 6:

Haplotype distribution within each locality and over Belgium

2.2 Comparison to published sequences

We compared the COI sequences from Belgium to previously published sequences (from Cesari et al., 2018 and Yan et al., 2021).

For COI, 441 sequences were retrieved from the study of Yan et al. (2021) and 168 from Cesari et al. (2018).

Iteration: 1 Number of links: 58 Iteration: 2 Number of links: 63 Iteration: 3 Number of li

The haplotype network is quite messy due to the number of haplotypes (59)

Figure 7:

Haplotype network by country (sqrt of haplotype freq; Haplotype codes are masked) The haplotype network

is quite messy due to the number of haplotypes (59)

Part of haplotypes found in Belgium are very common haplotypes (present in China and in many invaded countries), but others likely originates from Japan and/or Italy. These latter haplotypes could have been introduced in Belgium directly from Japan or from invasive Italian populations ('bridgehead effect').

Figure 8:

Haplotype network by country with haplotype codes (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 9:

Haplotype network by country categories (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 10:

Haplotype network by country categories (sqrt of haplotype freq)

	Belgium	Invaded	Native-China	Native-Japan
H01	33	327	26	0
H02	0	0	5	0
H03	23	41	9	0
H08	25	12	0	0
H15	0	0	1	0
H22	0	0	13	0
H23	1	0	0	9
H27	0	0	0	2
H32	0	1	0	0
H33	0	6	21	0
H39	0	0	0	2
H40	0	0	0	1
H40c	1	9	0	0
H41	2	2	0	3
H41c	8	26	0	0
H42c	5	4	0	0
H43	0	0	0	2
H43c	0	10	0	0
H44	0	1	0	0
H45	0	0	0	11
H47	0	1	0	0
H48	0	3	0	0
H49c	1	2	0	0
N01	0	0	1	0
N03	0	0	1	0
N04	0	0	1	0
N05	0	0	4	0
N06	0	0	4	0
N07	0	0	1	0
N08	0	0	1	0
N09	0	0	1	0
N12	0	0	0	1
N13	0	0	0	1
N14	0	0	0	1
N15	0	0	0	1
N16	0	0	0	1
N21	0	0	0	1
N22	0	0	0	10
N24	0	0	0	1
N25	0	0	0	1
N26	0	0	0	1
N27	0	0	0	1
N28	0	0	1	0
N29	0	0	1	0
N30	0	0	1	0
N32	0	0	1	0
N33	0	0	1	0
N34	0	0	0	1
N35	0	0	0	1

	Belgium	Invaded	Native-China	Native-Japan
N36	0	0	0	1
N37	0	0	0	1
N38	0	0	0	1
N39	0	0	0	2
N40	0	0	0	6
N41	0	0	0	2
N43	0	0	0	2
N45	0	0	0	1
N46	0	0	0	1
N47	0	1	0	0

Haplotype distribution by country categories

Country	N	Hn	h	π	D	pval D	R2	pval R2
Austria	16	4	0.70	0.003	-0.517	0.605	0.129	0.362
Belgium	99	9	0.77	0.004	0.258	0.796	0.106	0.657
Chile	31	2	0.06	0.000	-1.145	0.252	0.177	0.924
China	94	19	0.85	0.004	-1.291	0.197	0.055	0.129
Georgia	31	1	0.00	0.000	/	/	/	/
Greece	9	3	0.56	0.003	0.881	0.378	0.21	0.844
Hungary	92	3	0.12	0.000	-1.697	0.09	0.084	0.426
Italy	176	12	0.68	0.004	-0.373	0.709	0.075	0.44
Japan	69	29	0.93	0.004	-1.701	0.089	0.044	0.032
Romania	30	1	0.00	0.000	/	/	/	/
Serbia	10	2	0.56	0.001	1.464	0.143	0.278	0.95
Slovenia	16	3	0.49	0.001	-0.966	0.334	0.19	0.9
Turkey	11	1	0.00	0.000	/	/	/	/
United States	24	1	0.00	0.000	/	/	/	/

Summary table of *cox1* MtDNA diversity by locality. N = sample size, Hn = number of haplotypes, h = haplotype diversity and π = nucleotide diversity, D = Tajima's D, pval D = p-value of Tajima's test, R2 = Ramos-Onsins and Rozas's R, pval R2 = p-value of R2's neutrality test.

Compared to other countries, Belgium shows a relatively high level of genetic diversity (h and π). Neutrality tests (based on Tajima's D and Ramos-Onsins and Rozas's R2 statistics) are reported for informative purpose only since the very recent introduction of *H. halys* could not already leave a genetic signal at the population level.

Figure 11:

To further investigate the demographic history of *H. halys* population in Belgium, we plotted the pairwise distribution of sequence mismatches (i.e. mutations). Episodes of population growth and decline leave characteristic wave signatures in the distribution of nucleotide (or restriction) site differences between pairs of individuals. In equilibrium populations, frequency curves are theoretically free of waves but simulations showed that many peaks may characterize such populations. Thus it is easier to spot a non-equilibrium population with a clear wave (shifting to the right with time spent since demographic event happened at rate $1/2u - u =$ mutation rate per region of DNA under study, thus multiplied by the number of nt under study) (Rogers and Harpending 1992).

Neutrality tests revealed that, according to R2 statistic, only Japan showed signs of demographic expansion

($R^2 = 0.044$, $p\text{val} < 0.05$; see above). Consistent with this, a wave is present in the mismatch distribution, centered on 2-3 mutations. According to a mutation rate (per nt) of 6.2×10^{-8} (Haag-Liautard et al. 2008), the demographic expansion in Japanese population of *H. halys* can be estimated around $2.5 \times 10^5 / 2 \times 6.2 \times 10^{-8} = \sim 30,000$ generations. Thus, 20,000 to 10,000 years ago (with 2 or 3 generations/year, respectively).

3 COII Analysis

3.1 Data from Belgium

95 sequences were retrieved for COII fragment analysis with 5 distinct haplotypes. Haplotype diversity (i.e. the probability that two randomly chosen haplotypes are different; Nei & Tajima, 1981), $h = 0.7 \pm 0.01$. Nucleotide diversity (i.e. the average number of nucleotide differences per site between two DNA sequences from the population/sample of interest; Nei & Li, 1979), $\pi = 0.0021 \pm 0.0015$

```
##
## Haplotypes extracted from: d
##
##      Number of haplotypes: 5
##      Sequence length: 518
##
## Haplotype labels and frequencies:
##
##   I  II III  IV  V
##  30  2  31   2  30
##
## Less than 6 observations: doing complete enumeration.
## Iteration: 1Iteration: 2Iteration: 3Iteration: 4Iteration: 5Iteration: 6Iteration: 7Iteration:
```


Figure 12:

Size the haplotypes according to their frequencies (square-rooted)

Figure 13:

Haplotype network by region (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 14:

Haplotype network by locality (sqrt of haplotype freq)

	h01	h03	h11	h15	h21
Ezemaal	1	0	0	0	0
Heverlee	4	1	0	0	1
Jeuk	0	0	1	0	0
Kerkom	0	1	0	0	0
Kessel-Lo	5	1	1	0	0
Lesdain	0	2	0	0	0
Lummen	0	1	0	0	0
Melen	1	1	0	0	0
Mouscron	0	0	1	0	0
Neufchateau	0	1	0	0	0
Nieuwenhoven	1	0	0	0	0
Rhisnes	0	2	0	0	1
Rik Gentbrugge	9	13	26	0	0
Rosoux	2	0	0	0	0
Sint-Lambrechts-Herk	3	1	0	0	0
Upigny	1	1	0	0	0
Vlijtingen	3	6	1	2	0

Haplotype distribution by locality

Figure 15:

Haplotype distribution within each locality and over Belgium

3.2 Comparison to published sequences

We compared the sequences from Belgium to previously published sequences (from Cesari et al., 2018 and Yan et al., 2021).

For the COII, 450 sequences were retrieved from the study of Yan et al. (2021) and 201 from Cesari et al. (2018).

Iteration: 1 Number of links: 29 Iteration: 2 Number of links: 30 Iteration: 3 Number of li

Figure 16:

Haplotype network by country (sqrt of haplotype freq; Haplotype codes are masked)

- Austria
- Belgium
- Chile
- China
- Georgia
- Greece
- Hungary
- Italy
- Japan
- Romania
- Serbia
- Slovenia
- Switzerland
- Turkey
- United States

Figure 17:

Haplotype network by country with haplotype codes (sqrt of haplotype freq)

● Belgium ● Native-China
● Invaded ● Native-Japan

Figure 18:

Haplotype network by country categories (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 19:

Haplotype network by country categories (sqrt of haplotype freq)

	Belgium	Invaded	Native-China	Native-Japan
h01	30	353	26	0
h03	31	107	46	0
h04	0	0	5	0
h05	0	0	3	0
h11	30	20	0	56
h15	2	2	0	1
h16	0	0	0	1
h17	0	0	0	1
h18	0	0	0	3
h21	2	1	0	0
n01	0	0	1	0
n02	0	0	0	1
n03	0	0	2	0
n04	0	0	1	0
n05	0	0	3	0
n06	0	0	1	0
n08	0	0	0	1
n10	0	0	1	0
n11	0	0	0	1
n12	0	0	0	1
n13	0	0	0	2
n14	0	0	0	1
n15	0	0	1	0
n16	0	0	1	0
n17	0	0	2	0
n18	0	0	2	0
n19	0	0	1	0
n20	0	0	1	0
n22	0	0	1	0
n23	0	0	1	0

Haplotype distribution by country categories

Country	N	Hn	h	π	D	pval D	R2	pval R2
Austria	15	3	0.53	0.0011	-0.105	0.916	0.148	0.548
Belgium	95	5	0.7	0.0021	0.528	0.597	0.123	0.805
Chile	31	2	0.06	1e-04	-1.145	0.252	0.177	0.925
China	99	18	0.72	0.0023	-1.948	0.051	0.031	0.003
Georgia	33	1	0	0	/	/	/	/
Greece	9	2	0.56	0.0011	1.401	0.161	0.278	0.955
Hungary	90	3	0.11	3e-04	-1.426	0.154	0.071	0.305
Italy	211	5	0.57	0.0013	0.016	0.987	0.086	0.607
Japan	69	11	0.34	0.001	-2.147	0.032	0.035	0.005
Romania	31	1	0	0	/	/	/	/
Serbia	9	2	0.56	0.0011	1.401	0.161	0.278	0.966
Slovenia	15	2	0.48	9e-04	1.122	0.262	0.238	0.972
Switzerland	1	1	/	/	/	/	/	/
Turkey	13	1	0	0	/	/	/	/
United States	25	1	0	0	/	/	/	/

Summary table of *cox2* MtDNA diversity by locality. N = sample size, Hn = number of haplotypes, h = haplotype diversity and π = nucleotide diversity, D = Tajima's D, pval D = p-value of Tajima's test, R2 = Ramos-Onsins and Rozas's R, pval R2 = p-value of R2's neutrality test.

Figure 20:

Pairwise distribution of mismatches (nt differences) between sequences for Belgium, Italy, China and Japan. We can't see any obvious wave pattern in any country. Interestingly, Neutrality tests indicate significant population expansion for both China and Japan (see Table above), while this is not visible on the mismatch plots.

4 COI + COII Analysis

4.1 Data from Belgium

COI and COII sequences were concatenated and analysed together. 95 concatenated sequences were analysed with 12 distinct haplotypes. Haplotype diversity (i.e. the probability that two randomly chosen haplotypes are different; Nei & Tajima, 1981), $h = 0.79 \pm 0.02$. Nucleotide diversity (i.e. the average number of nucleotide differences per site between two DNA sequences from the population/sample of interest; Nei & Li, 1979), $\pi = 0.0031 \pm 0.0018$

##

Haplotypes extracted from: d

##

Number of haplotypes: 12

Sequence length: 1176

##

Haplotype labels and frequencies:

##

##	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
##	21	30	1	8	1	24	4	1	1	1	2	1

Iteration: 1 Number of links: 11Iteration: 2 Number of links: 12Iteration: 3 Number of li

Figure 21:

Simple haplotype network using the number of different nucleotides between haplotypes to compute the distance matrix. Network constructed using the randomized minimum spanning tree method (rmst; Paradis, 2018).

Figure 22:

Size the haplotypes according to their frequencies (square-rooted)

Figure 23:

Haplotype network by region (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 24:

Haplotype network by locality (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 25:

Haplotype distribution within each locality and over Belgium

We tested isolation by distance (IBD) using Mantel test between a matrix of genetic distances (euclidean) and a matrix of geographic distances between pairs of individuals.

```
## Monte-Carlo test
## Call: mantel.randtest(m1 = Dgen, m2 = Dgeo)
##
## Observation: 0.1450696
##
## Based on 999 replicates
## Simulated p-value: 0.001
## Alternative hypothesis: greater
##
##      Std.Obs  Expectation  Variance
## 5.281109e+00 -7.738057e-06 7.546557e-04
```


Figure 26:

Our results indicate significant IBD, hence some genetic structuring, is present at the scale of Belgium when we compare specimens of *H. halys*.

```
##
## Converting data from a genind to a genpop object...
##
## ...done.
## Monte-Carlo test
```

```
## Call: mantel.randtest(m1 = Dgen, m2 = Dgeo)
##
## Observation: 0.06146072
##
## Based on 999 replicates
## Simulated p-value: 0.338
## Alternative hypothesis: greater
##
##      Std.Obs Expectation      Variance
## 0.348172147 0.001281722 0.029874578
```


Figure 27:

In contrast, when we compare populations (using Edwards' distance -Euclidean), the Mantel test is not significant.

4.2 Comparison to published sequences

We compared the sequences from Belgium to previously published sequences (from Cesari et al., 2018 and Yan et al., 2021).

Iteration: 1 Number of links: 74 Iteration: 2 Number of links: 82 Iteration: 3 Number of li

Figure 28:

Haplotype network by country (sqrt of haplotype freq) Haplotype codes are masked

Figure 29:

Haplotype network by country with haplotype codes (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 30:

Haplotype network by country categories (sqrt of haplotype freq)

Figure 31:

Haplotype network by country categories (sqrt of haplotype freq)

	Belgium	Invaded	Native-China	Native-Japan
H01_h01	30	310	25	0
H01_h03	0	2	0	0
H01_h11	0	3	0	0
H01_n01	0	0	1	0
H02_h04	0	0	4	0
H03_h01	0	1	0	0
H03_h03	21	38	5	0
H03_h05	0	0	3	0
H03_h11	1	0	0	0
H03_h21	1	1	0	0
H03_n20	0	0	1	0
H08_h03	0	1	0	0
H08_h11	24	10	0	0
H08_h21	1	0	0	0
H15_n16	0	0	1	0
H22_h03	0	0	11	0
H22_n10	0	0	1	0
H22_n23	0	0	1	0
H23_h11	1	0	0	8
H23_n08	0	0	0	1
H27_h11	0	0	0	2
H32_h01	0	1	0	0
H33_h03	0	5	20	0
H39_h18	0	0	0	2
H40_n02	0	0	0	1
H40c_h03	1	8	0	0
H41_h15	2	2	0	1
H41_h16	0	0	0	1
H41_h17	0	0	0	1
H41c_h01	0	1	0	0
H41c_h03	8	23	0	0
H42c_h11	4	2	0	0
H43_h11	0	0	0	2
H43c_h03	0	9	0	0
H44_h01	0	1	0	0
H45_h11	0	0	0	9
H45_n11	0	0	0	1
H47_h01	0	1	0	0
H48_h03	0	3	0	0
H49c_h03	1	2	0	0
N01_h03	0	0	1	0
N03_n03	0	0	1	0
N04_n04	0	0	1	0
N05_n03	0	0	1	0
N05_n05	0	0	3	0
N06_h03	0	0	2	0
N06_n17	0	0	2	0
N07_h03	0	0	1	0
N08_n15	0	0	1	0

	Belgium	Invaded	Native-China	Native-Japan
N09_n18	0	0	1	0
N12_n13	0	0	0	1
N13_h11	0	0	0	1
N14_h11	0	0	0	1
N15_n13	0	0	0	1
N16_h11	0	0	0	1
N21_h11	0	0	0	1
N22_h11	0	0	0	9
N22_n14	0	0	0	1
N25_h18	0	0	0	1
N26_h11	0	0	0	1
N27_h11	0	0	0	1
N28_h04	0	0	1	0
N30_h03	0	0	1	0
N32_h01	0	0	1	0
N34_n12	0	0	0	1
N35_h11	0	0	0	1
N36_h11	0	0	0	1
N37_h11	0	0	0	1
N39_h11	0	0	0	1
N40_h11	0	0	0	6
N41_h11	0	0	0	2
N43_h11	0	0	0	2
N45_h11	0	0	0	1
N46_h11	0	0	0	1
N47_h03	0	1	0	0

Haplotype distribution by country categories

Country	N	Hn	h	π	D	pval D	R2	pval R2
Austria	15	4	0.69	0.002	-0.473	0.637	0.134	0.413
Belgium	95	12	0.79	0.003	0.336	0.737	0.109	0.688
Chile	31	2	0.06	0.000	-1.506	0.132	0.177	0.933
China	90	24	0.86	0.003	-1.576	0.115	0.047	0.075
Georgia	31	1	0.00	0.000	/	/	/	/
Greece	8	3	0.61	0.002	1.238	0.216	0.23	0.859
Hungary	90	3	0.11	0.000	-1.957	0.05	0.08	0.359
Italy	161	18	0.72	0.003	-0.432	0.666	0.074	0.408
Japan	65	32	0.94	0.002	-1.977	0.048	0.036	0.003
Romania	30	1	0.00	0.000	/	/	/	/
Serbia	9	2	0.56	0.001	1.754	0.079	0.278	0.972
Slovenia	15	3	0.51	0.001	-0.407	0.684	0.177	0.813
Turkey	11	1	0.00	0.000	/	/	/	/
United States	24	1	0.00	0.000	/	/	/	/

Summary table of MtDNA diversity by locality. N = sample size, Hn = number of haplotypes, h = haplotype diversity and π = nucleotide diversity, D = Tajima's D, pval D = p-value of Tajima's neutrality test, R2 = Ramos-Onsins and Rozas's R, pval R2 = p-value of R2's neutrality test.

Figure 32:

As expected, pairwise mismatch plots are intermediate between COI and COII. Only sequences from Japan still display a wave characteristic of population expansion.

Iteration: 1 Number of links: 20 Iteration: 2 Number of links: 22 Iteration: 3 Number of li

Figure 33:

Comparison of sequences from Belgium to sequences from Italy by region. Since only Belgian and Italian sequences are close to Japanese haplotypes, we wanted to test whether all Belgian sequences may come from a single Italian region, putative source of invasive Belgian *H. halys* population. This is apparently not the case and rarer haplotypes found in Belgium are shared with the Veneto region but also with the Lombardy and Piedmont regions.

	BE- Flanders	BE- Wallonia	IT- Calabria	IT- Emilia- Romagna	IT-Friuli- Venezia Giulia	IT- Friuli VG	IT- Lazio	IT- Liguria	IT- Lombardy	IT- Piedmont	IT- Trentino- ST	IT- Tuscany	IT- Veneto
H01h01	26	4	0	17	21	10	0	0	15	5	5	2	5
H01h03	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H01h11	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
H03h01	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H03h03	15	6	1	3	0	0	1	0	7	1	2	0	1
H03h11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H03h21	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
H08h03	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
H08h11	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	1	0	0	0
H08h21	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H23h11	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H40ch03	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0
H41ch01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
H41ch03	7	1	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	16	0	1	0
H41h15	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H42ch11	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H43ch03	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	6	0	0	0
H44h01	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H47h01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H48h03	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
H49ch03	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0

```

## R version 4.0.2 (2020-06-22)
## Platform: x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64 (64-bit)
## Running under: Windows 10 x64 (build 19045)
##
## Matrix products: default
##
## locale:
## [1] LC_COLLATE=French_Belgium.1252 LC_CTYPE=French_Belgium.1252
## [3] LC_MONETARY=French_Belgium.1252 LC_NUMERIC=C
## [5] LC_TIME=French_Belgium.1252
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods   base
##
## other attached packages:
## [1] adegenet_2.1.5  ade4_1.7-19      mapplots_1.5.1  sf_1.0-4        pegas_1.1
## [6] ape_5.6-1      tidyr_1.2.0      dplyr_1.0.7     ggplot2_3.3.5   kableExtra_1.3.4
## [11] pander_0.6.3   knitr_1.30
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] httr_1.4.2      splines_4.0.2    viridisLite_0.3.0  shiny_1.7.1
## [5] assertthat_0.2.1  highr_0.8        yaml_2.2.1         gdttools_0.2.2
## [9] pillar_1.6.5     lattice_0.20-41  glue_1.6.2         digest_0.6.25
## [13] promises_1.2.0.1  rvest_1.0.2      colorspace_1.4-1   Matrix_1.2-18
## [17] htmltools_0.5.2  httpuv_1.6.3     plyr_1.8.6         pkgconfig_2.0.3
## [21] bookdown_0.21    purrr_0.3.4      xtable_1.8-4       scales_1.1.1
## [25] webshot_0.5.2    svglite_1.2.3.2  later_1.1.0.1     cpp11_0.4.2
## [29] tibble_3.0.3     mgcv_1.8-33      generics_0.1.0     ellipsis_0.3.2
## [33] withr_2.4.3      cli_3.1.1        magrittr_2.0.1     crayon_1.4.2
## [37] mime_0.9         evaluate_0.14    fansi_0.4.1        nlme_3.1-149
## [41] MASS_7.3-53     xml2_1.3.2       class_7.3-17       vegan_2.5-7
## [45] tools_4.0.2      lifecycle_1.0.1  stringr_1.4.0     munsell_0.5.0
## [49] cluster_2.1.0    compiler_4.0.2   e1071_1.7-3        systemfonts_0.3.1
## [53] rlang_1.0.2      classInt_0.4-3   units_0.6-7        grid_4.0.2
## [57] rstudioapi_0.13  igraph_1.3.0     rmarkdown_2.19     gtable_0.3.0
## [61] codetools_0.2-16 DBI_1.1.0        reshape2_1.4.4     R6_2.4.1
## [65] fastmap_1.1.0    seqinr_4.2-8     utf8_1.1.4         KernSmooth_2.23-17
## [69] permute_0.9-5    stringi_1.5.3    parallel_4.0.2     Rcpp_1.0.7
## [73] vctrs_0.3.8     tidyrselect_1.1.0  xfun_0.30

```